

SMAUG 1st Newsletter!

Explore the [SMAUG EU](#) world and learn the latest project news!

Let us introduce ourselves!

The **SMAUG** (Smart Maritime And Underwater Guardian) project kicked off on the **2nd of October** in Valencia during a two-day meeting! With a starting date in October 2023 and a **duration of three years**, the SMAUG project is on a mission to **improve the underwater detection of threats in ports and their entrance routes** using an integrated system capable of providing data concerning threat analysis between **3 main** elements:

- **Ports security infrastructure,**
- **Advanced underwater detection systems and**
- **Surveillance vessels.**

Explore the SMAUG kick-off meeting!

The scene in the maritime environment and the SMAUG solution.

The constant increase in maritime environment activity requires strong and efficient port security procedures to be implemented. This is particularly **crucial for identifying and surveilling legitimate and illicit operations in border, coastal, and port regions**. New techniques in drug smuggling and illegal activities taking place in the maritime environment are currently generating more challenges for law enforcement, as current detection means may often be no longer effective, while technological updates and improvements in prevention mechanisms are deemed mandatory. Countertrafficking organisations demand significant penetration to combat these issues, but sometimes they lack resources. As much as illegal activity is a focus for maritime security, monitoring legal activity is also paramount, especially concerning customs, operational and border management.

The primary goal of SMAUG, hence, is to improve and enhance the security of ports and their entrance routes, leveraging the power of Artificial Intelligence (AI), using an integrated system capable of providing data concerning threat detection and analysis between 3 main elements: ports security infrastructure, advanced underwater detection systems and surveillance vessels.

Learn about SMAUG's objectives, methodology, challenges and more on the project's website and

ABOUT

USE CASES

SMAUG team!

The SMAUG consortium comprises **22** highly experienced partners across **7 EU** countries (***Spain, Italy, France, Germany, Greece, Norway, Estonia***) under Indra's coordination. The team includes ***Universities, Research Centres, SMEs, Law Enforcement Agencies, Public authorities, Coastal / Border guards and Private organisations.***

Meet the team behind the SMAUG project!

SMAUG latest news!

The SMAUG project is currently in its fifth month of implementation. Even though it is in its early implementation steps, partners have already started working towards the SMAUG objectives. Activities, including *legal and ethical dimensions, maritime security information management, underwater detection and location, as well as outreach, exploitation and collaboration*, have kicked off, and the first results are expected soon!

Until then, embark on the SMAUG project and explore a short maritime transportation history

Maritime transportation history

Events participation.

The SMAUG project participated and spread the word about the project at the **47th Scandinavian Symposium on Physical Acoustics!**

Learn more

If you want to explore the SMAUG project further, then read the project's 1st Press Release!

What's next?

The SMAUG project will continue to work towards the achievement of its goals! In the meantime, it will publish blog articles, participate in events, conferences, and workshops, and collaborate with relevant EU projects, maximising its impact and reach and assisting in future research.

Join the SMAUG project's journey by following its social media profiles!

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SMAUG EU project

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